

Two- and Three-Dimensional Osteometric Variability of the Foramen Magnum in Modern Humans

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Supplementary Material, Materials – S2.1
Provenience and Collection Information for the Eritrean Skull Series

Tab. S2.1: Berlin specimens from Kohaito, Eritrea, North-Eastern Africa – general information.							
ID	Continent	Country	Ethnicity	Collector, Year	Period	Sex	Remarks / Reference
RV 1065	Africa	Kohaito plateau	Galla tribe?	Max Schoeller, 1894	1096 ± 52 calAD	M	ID card; Strauch #2496; (Jungklaus, 2017; Schoeller, 1895; Schweinfurth, 1984; Wenig, 2006; Wenig and Vogt, 2017)
RV 1283	Africa	Kohaito plateau	Galla tribe?	Max Schoeller, 1894	1375 ± 47 calAD	F	ID card; Strauch #2496; (Jungklaus, 2017; Schoeller, 1895; Schweinfurth, 1984; Wenig, 2006; Wenig and Vogt, 2017)
RV 1284	Africa	Kohaito plateau	Galla tribe?	Max Schoeller, 1894	1240 ± 29 calAD	M	ID card; Strauch #2496; (Jungklaus, 2017; Schoeller, 1895; Schweinfurth, 1984; Wenig, 2006; Wenig and Vogt, 2017)
RV 1285	Africa	Kohaito plateau	Galla tribe?	Max Schoeller, 1894	11 th to 15 th century AD*	F	ID card; Strauch #2496; (Jungklaus, 2017; Schoeller, 1895; Schweinfurth, 1984; Wenig, 2006; Wenig and Vogt, 2017)
RV 1288	Africa	Kohaito plateau	Galla tribe?	Max Schoeller, 1894	11 th to 15 th century AD*	M	ID card; Strauch #2496; (Jungklaus, 2017; Schoeller, 1895; Schweinfurth, 1984; Wenig, 2006; Wenig and Vogt, 2017)
RV 1289	Africa	Kohaito plateau	Galla tribe?	Max Schoeller, 1894	11 th to 15 th century AD*	M	ID card; Strauch #2496; (Jungklaus, 2017; Schoeller, 1895; Schweinfurth, 1984; Wenig, 2006; Wenig and Vogt, 2017)
RV 1290	Africa	Kohaito plateau	Galla tribe?	Max Schoeller, 1894	11 th to 15 th century AD*	F	ID card; Strauch #2496; (Jungklaus, 2017; Schoeller, 1895; Schweinfurth, 1984; Wenig, 2006; Wenig and Vogt, 2017)
RV 1291	Africa	Kohaito plateau	Galla tribe?	Max Schoeller, 1894	11 th to 15 th century AD*	M	ID card; Strauch #2496; (Jungklaus, 2017; Schoeller, 1895; Schweinfurth, 1984; Wenig, 2006; Wenig and Vogt, 2017)
RV 1293	Africa	Kohaito plateau	Galla tribe?	Max Schoeller, 1894	11 th to 15 th century AD*	M	ID card; Strauch #2496; (Jungklaus, 2017; Schoeller, 1895; Schweinfurth, 1984; Wenig, 2006; Wenig and Vogt, 2017)
RV 1294	Africa	Kohaito plateau	Galla tribe?	Max Schoeller, 1894	11 th to 15 th century AD*	F	ID card; Strauch #2496; (Jungklaus, 2017; Schoeller, 1895; Schweinfurth, 1984; Wenig, 2006; Wenig and Vogt, 2017)
RV 1296	Africa	Kohaito plateau	Galla tribe?	Max Schoeller, 1894	1112 ± 60 calAD	M	ID card; Strauch #2496; (Jungklaus, 2017; Schoeller, 1895; Schweinfurth, 1984; Wenig, 2006; Wenig and Vogt, 2017)
RV 1298	Africa	Kohaito plateau	Galla tribe?	Max Schoeller, 1894	11 th to 15 th century AD*	F	ID card; Strauch #2496; (Jungklaus, 2017; Schoeller, 1895; Schweinfurth, 1984; Wenig, 2006; Wenig and Vogt, 2017)
RV 1300	Africa	Kohaito plateau	Galla tribe?	Max Schoeller, 1894	11 th to 15 th century AD*	M	ID card; Strauch #2496; (Jungklaus, 2017; Schoeller, 1895; Schweinfurth, 1984; Wenig, 2006; Wenig and Vogt, 2017)
RV 1301	Africa	Kohaito plateau	Galla tribe?	Max Schoeller, 1894	11 th to 15 th century AD*	M	ID card; Strauch #2496; (Jungklaus, 2017; Schoeller, 1895; Schweinfurth, 1984; Wenig, 2006; Wenig and Vogt, 2017)
RV 1302	Africa	Kohaito plateau	Galla tribe?	Max Schoeller, 1894	11 th to 15 th century AD*	F	ID card; Strauch #2496; (Jungklaus, 2017; Schoeller, 1895; Schweinfurth, 1984; Wenig, 2006; Wenig and Vogt, 2017)
RV 1303	Africa	Kohaito plateau	Galla tribe?	Max Schoeller, 1894	11 th to 15 th century AD*	M	ID card; Strauch #2496; (Jungklaus, 2017; Schoeller, 1895; Schweinfurth, 1984; Wenig, 2006; Wenig and Vogt, 2017)
RV 1304	Africa	Kohaito plateau	Galla tribe?	Max Schoeller, 1894	11 th to 15 th century AD*	ind	ID card; Strauch #2496; (Jungklaus, 2017; Schoeller, 1895; Schweinfurth, 1984; Wenig, 2006; Wenig and Vogt, 2017)
RV 1305	Africa	Kohaito plateau	Galla tribe?	Max Schoeller, 1894	11 th to 15 th century AD*	ind	ID card; Strauch #2496; (Jungklaus, 2017; Schoeller, 1895; Schweinfurth, 1984; Wenig, 2006; Wenig and Vogt, 2017)
RV 1306	Africa	Kohaito plateau	Galla tribe?	Max Schoeller, 1894	1336 ± 45 calAD	M	ID card; Strauch #2496; (Jungklaus, 2017; Schoeller, 1895; Schweinfurth, 1984; Wenig, 2006; Wenig and Vogt, 2017)
RV 1307	Africa	Kohaito plateau	Galla tribe?	Max Schoeller, 1894	11 th to 15 th century AD*	F	ID card; Strauch #2496; (Jungklaus, 2017; Schoeller, 1895; Schweinfurth, 1984; Wenig, 2006; Wenig and Vogt, 2017)
RV 1309	Africa	Kohaito plateau	Galla tribe?	Max Schoeller, 1894	11 th to 15 th century AD*	M	ID card; Strauch #2496; (Jungklaus, 2017; Schoeller, 1895; Schweinfurth, 1984; Wenig, 2006; Wenig and Vogt, 2017)

RV = Rudolf-Virchow-Collection identification number, F = female, M = male, ind = sex indeterminable, ID card = Karteikarte (), Strauch # = identification number in Strauch-Catalogue, DB = database of the Berlin anthropological collections, ZfE = Zeitschrift für Ethnologie (Journal of Ethnology), * = probable dating according to the radiocarbon dating results of some of the Kohaito skulls. calAD = calibrated radiocarbon date, ? = unsure information.

Supplementary Material, Materials – S2.2
Provenience and Collection Information for the Japanese Skull Series

Tab. 2.2: Berlin specimens from Japan, East Asia – general information.

ID	Continent	Origin	Ethnicity	Collector, Year	Period	Sex	Remarks / Reference
RV 37	Asia	N/A	Japanese	Dr. Unkes von Langen / Langegg ded.	N/A	F	Marked as ♀ (female) / Strauch #36; DB
RV 1067	Asia	N/A	N/A	Tagutzi ded.	N/A	M	Strauch #1634; DB
RV 2148	Asia	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	ind	Strauch #?; DB
S 4033	Asia	N/A	N/A	Dönitz lgt.	N/A	F	DB
S 4034	Asia	N/A	N/A	Dönitz lgt.	N/A	ind	DB
S 4035	Asia	N/A	N/A	Dönitz lgt.	N/A	M	DB
S 4036	Asia	Honshū, Kantō, Tokio	N/A	Dönitz lgt.	N/A	F	DB
S 4037	Asia	N/A	N/A	Dönitz lgt.	N/A	F	DB
S 4038	Asia	N/A	N/A	Dönitz lgt.	N/A	ind	41 Jahre / DB
S 4039	Asia	N/A	N/A	Dönitz lgt.	N/A	M	DB
S 4632	Asia	Honshū, Kōbe, Hyōgo, Kinki (Kansai)	Japanese	von Hansemann leg.	N/A	M	45 Jahre / DB

RV = Rudolf-Virchow-Collection identification number, S = Felix-von-Luschan-Collection identification number, N/A = information not available, F = female, M = male, ind = sex indeterminable, ID card = Karteikarte, Strauch # = identification number in Strauch-Catalogue, DB = database of the Berlin anthropological collections. ded. = dedication (Latin for "has donated"), leg. = legit (Latin for "has collected")

Supplementary Material, Materials – S2.3

Provenience and Collection Information for the German Skull Series

Tab. S2.3: Berlin specimens from Germany, Central Europe – general information.							
ID	Continent	Country	Ethnicity	Collector, Year	Period	Sex	Remarks / Reference
RV 376	Europe	Brandenburg, Reitwein (Oder)	German	Graf von Finckenstein, 1892?	9 th – 11 th century AD	M	Male according to Virchow / DB; Reitwein #3; Strauch #890; ZfE 24, 1892, 550-555 (Virchow, 1892)
RV 389	Europe	Berlin, Michaelkirchplatz	German	Graf v. Finckenstein, 1889	N/A	M	DB; Strauch #878
RV 613	Europe	Bavaria, Franconia	German	N/A	N/A	F	DB; Strauch #979; Franken #2
RV 614	Europe	Bavaria, Franconia	German	N/A	N/A	M	DB; Strauch #972
RV 615	Europe	Bavaria, Franconia	German	N/A	N/A	ind	DB; Strauch #973
RV 721	Europe	Bremen	German	N/A	N/A	F	DB; Strauch #1068; Bremen #3; ZfE 6, 1874, 239-251 (Virchow, 1874a) (match unsure)
RV 724	Europe	Bremen	German	Blüncker?	N/A	M	DB; Strauch #1071; ZfE 6, 1874, 239-251 (Virchow, 1874a) (match unsure)
RV 725	Europe	Bremen, rathskeller	German	N/A	N/A	ind	"Bremen Ratskeller" / DB; Strauch #1072; ZfE 6, 1874, 239-251 (Virchow, 1874a) (match unsure)
RV 726	Europe	Bremen	German	N/A	N/A	F	DB; Strauch #1073; Bremen #5; ZfE 6, 1874, 239-251 (Virchow, 1874a) (match unsure)
RV 778	Europe	Hamburg, Bergdorf-Vierlande; churchyard of Kurslack	German	Dr. Th. Simon	Middle Ages?	F	Female according to Virchow / DB; Vierlande #1; Strauch #1077; ZfE 6, 1874, 244 (Virchow, 1874a)
RV 782	Europe	Lower Saxony, Meppen-Kirchhof	German	1877?	N/A	F	DB; Strauch #1007; Meppen-Kirchhof #2
RV 783	Europe	Lower Saxony, Meppen churchyard	German	1877	N/A	M	DB; Strauch #1012
RV 786	Europe	Bavaria, Simbach-Hauersdorf	German	leg. Dr. Hackenbreit; ded. Dr. Heyer 1845	N/A	ind	DB; Strauch #1004
RV 834	Europe	Lower Saxony, Meppen	German	N/A	N/A	ind	DB; Strauch #1010; Meppen #1
RV 870	Europe	Lower Saxony, Meppen	German	N/A	N/A	M	DB; Strauch #1013
RV 872	Europe	Lower Saxony, Meppen	German	N/A	N/A	ind	DB; Strauch #1016
RV 879	Europe	Saxony-Anhalt, Magdeburg	German	N/A	N/A	M	DB; Strauch #2586
RV 884	Europe	Lower Saxony, Oldenburg	German	ded. Dr. Meyer	N/A	M	DB; Strauch #1027; Oldenburg #1
RV 886	Europe	Lower Saxony, Oldenburg, Ankum	German	ded. Dr. Meyer	N/A	F	DB; Strauch #1022; Oldenburg #3
RV 890	Europe	Lower Saxony, Oldenburg	German	N/A	N/A	F	DB; Strauch #1019; Oldenburg #7
RV 899	Europe	Saxony-Anhalt, Aschersleben	German	Ded. Past. Becker, 1886	N/A	M	Male according to Virchow / DB; Strauch #1038; Aschersleben #6; ZfE 18, 1886, 63-67 (Virchow, 1886)
RV 901	Europe	North Rhine-Westphalia, Westphalia	German	Prof. Laudois (Tourtal-Musuem, Münster)	N/A	M	DB; Strauch #1032; Westfalen #2
RV 903	Europe	North Rhine-Westphalia, Münster	German	N/A, 1830	N/A	M	DB; Strauch #1029
RV 905	Europe	Brandenburg	German	N/A	N/A	ind	DB; Strauch #1043

RV 923	Europe	Bavaria, Upper Bavaria	German	ded. Stadtrath Löwe	N/A	M	DB; Strauch #1431; Oberbayern #1
RV 959	Europe	Lower Saxony, Norderney	German	N/A	N/A	F	DB; Strauch #1494; Norderney #1
RV 1007	Europe	Bavaria, Franconia	German	N/A	N/A	M	DB; Strauch #971
RV 1124	Europe	Lower Saxony, Eastern Friesland	German	Hans Wehmeke?	N/A	M	DB; Strauch #1573
RV 1613	Europe	North Rhine-Westphalia, Dortmund	German	N/A	N/A	M	DB; Strauch #2261; Dortmund #1
RV 1615	Europe	North Rhine-Westphalia, Dortmund	German	N/A	N/A	F	DB; Strauch #2263; Dortmund #3
RV 1616	Europe	North Rhine-Westphalia, Dortmund	German	N/A	N/A	F	DB; Strauch #2264; Dortmund #4
RV 1618	Europe	North Rhine-Westphalia, Dortmund	German	N/A	N/A	F	DB; Strauch #2266; Dortmund #6
RV 1625	Europe	Thuringia, Sömmerda-Leubingen	German	ded. Prof. Kopffleisch, 1877	12/13 CE	M	Male according to Virchow / DB; Strauch #2034; Leubingen #5; ZfE 9, 1877, 327-330 (Virchow, 1877)
RV 1630	Europe	Lower Saxony, Ankum, Emsland	German	N/A	N/A	M	DB; Strauch #1060
RV 1633	Europe	Lower Saxony, Ankum, Emsland	German	N/A	N/A	M	DB; Strauch #1063
RV 1636	Europe	Lower Saxony, Ankum, Emsland	German	N/A	N/A	F	DB; Strauch #1066
RV 1638	Europe	Brandenburg, Brandenburg at the Havel	German	ded. Koeppek, 1869?	N/A	M	DB; Strauch #1896
RV 1639	Europe	Berlin	German	N/A	N/A	ind	DB; Strauch #2020
RV 1640	Europe	Northern Germany	German	1878	N/A	F	Female name, 27 years old / DB; Strauch #2026
RV 1656	Europe	Lower Saxony, Gerdau, Bohlsen, Lueneburg Heath	German	ded. Kühns, 1874	N/A	F	Female according to Virchow / DB; Strauch #2040; Bohlsen #3; ZfE 6, 1874, 31-40 (Virchow, 1874b)
RV 1657	Europe	Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania, Rostock, Marienkirche	German	1895	N/A	F	DB; Strauch #1826
S 158	Europe	Berlin, Spittelmarkt	German	N/A	N/A	M	DB
S 159	Europe	Berlin, Spittelmarkt	German	N/A	N/A	F	DB
S 162	Europe	Berlin, Spittelmarkt	German	N/A	N/A	M	DB
S 4541	Europe	Berlin	German	leg. von Hansemann	N/A	F	Female name, 58 years; ? #100 / DB
S 4585	Europe	Berlin	German	leg. von Hansemann	N/A	F	Female name, 21 years; ? #188 / DB
S 4631	Europe	Germany, Berlin	German	leg. v. Hansemann	N/A	F	Female name, 19 years, ? #243 / DB
S 5164	Europe	Germany, Berlin	German	leg. v. Hansemann, 1929	N/A	M	Male name / DB
S 5165	Europe	Germany, Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania, Perleberg, bog find	German	N/A	N/A	M	DB

RV = Rudolf-Virchow-Collection identification number, RSK = Former Racial Skull-Collection identification number, S = Felix-von-Luschan-Collection identification number, N/A = information not available, F = female, M = male, ind = sex indeterminable, Strauch # = identification number in Strauch-Catalogue, DB = database of the Berlin anthropological collections, ? = unknown identification number, ZfE = Zeitschrift für Ethnologie (Journal of Ethnology), ded. = dedication (Latin for "has donated"), leg. = legit (Latin for "has collected").

Supplementary Material, Materials – S2.4
Provenience and Collection Information for the Greek Skull Series

Tab. S2.4: Berlin specimens from Greece, South-Eastern Europe – general information.

ID	Continent	Country	Ethnicity	Collector, Year	Period	Sex	Remarks / Reference
RSK 501	Europe	Athens, Cemetery	Greek	N/A	N/A	M	NC1079,3 / AN25213; Broesike #107; DB
RSK 502	Europe	Athens, Cemetery	Greek	N/A	N/A	F	NC1079,4 / AN25214; Broesike #108; DB
RSK 503	Europe	Athens, Cemetery	Greek	N/A	N/A	M	NC1097,5 / AN25215; Broesike #109; DB
RSK 504	Europe	Athens, Cemetery	Greek	N/A	N/A	F	NC1079,6 / AN25216; Broesike #110; DB
RSK 505	Europe	Athens, Cemetery	Greek	N/A	N/A	F	NC1079,7 / AN25217; Broesike #111; DB
RSK 506	Europe	Athens, Cemetery	Greek	N/A	N/A	F	NC1079,8 / AN25219; Broesike #105; DB
RV 1119	Europe	Peloponnese, Pastros	Greek	Dimitrios?	N/A	F	Strauch #2007; ID card; DB
RV 1120	Europe	Peloponnese, Le(o)nidi	Greek	N/A	N/A	M	Strauch #2009, Lenidi #2; ID card; DB
RV 1121	Europe	Peloponnese, Le(o)nidi	Greek	N/A	N/A	ind	Strauch #2005; ID card; DB
RV 1122	Europe	Peloponnese, Le(o)nidi	Greek	N/A	N/A	M	Strauch #2006, Lenidi #4; ID card; DB
RV 1123	Europe	Peloponnese, Pastros	Greek	Dimitrios?	N/A	F	Strauch #1738; ID card; DB
RV 1842	Europe	Peloponnese, Le(o)nidi	Greek	N/A	N/A	M	Strauch #1735; ID card; DB
RV 1844	Europe	Peloponnese, Le(o)nidi	Greek	N/A	N/A	ind	Strauch #1741; Lenidi #2; ID card; DB
RV 1845	Europe	Peloponnese, Le(o)nidi	Greek	N/A	N/A	M	Strauch #1885; ID card; DB
RV 1846	Europe	Peloponnese, Pastros	Greek	N/A	N/A	M	Strauch #1740; ID card / DB
RV 1847	Europe	Peloponnese, Pastros	Greek	N/A	N/A	F	Strauch #1739; ID card; DB
RV 1848	Europe	Peloponnese, Pastros	Greek	N/A	N/A	ind	Strauch #1736; ID card; DB

RSK = Former Racial Skull-Collection identification number, RV = Rudolf-Virchow-Collection identification number, N/A = information not available, ? = unsure information, F = female, M = male, ind = sex indeterminable, ID cards = Karteikarte, Strauch # = identification number in Strauch-Catalogue, Broesike # = identification number in Broesike-Catalogue (Broesike, 1880), NC#/AN# = unknown identification number, DB = database of the Berlin anthropological collections.

Supplementary Material, Methods – S2.5 to S2.7

Morphological Sexing Supplements

Tab. S2.5: Traits for morphological sexing of the cranium and mandible after the method of Acsádi et al. (1970). The trait list was adopted from Sjøvold (1988) which is a modified version of the lists reported in Acsádi et al. (1970) and Ferembach et al. (1980).

	Nr.	Trait / Feature (English term)	Trait weight (w)
Cranium	1	Glabella	3
	2	Processus mastoideus (mastoid process)	3
	3	Planum nuchale relief (relief of the nuchal plane)	3
	4	Processus zygomaticus (zygomatic process)	3
	5	Arcus superciliaris (superciliary arch)	2
	6	Tubera frontalia and parietalia (frontal and parietal tuber)	2
	7	Protoburantia occipitalis externus (external occipital protuberance)	2
	8	Os zygomaticum (zygomatic bone)	2
	9	Crista supramastoidea (supramastoid crest)	2
	10	Margo supraorbitalis (supraorbital margin)	1
	11	Os frontale inclination (inclination of the frontal bone)	1
	12	Orbitae form (form of the orbit)	1
Mandible	13	General aspect (of the mandible)	3
	14	Trigonum mandibulae (mental protuberance)	2
	15	Angulus mandibulae (mandible angle)	1
	16	Margo inferior (inferior margin)	1
	17	Processus Condylaris (condyle process)	1

Tab. S2.6: Degree of trait expressions for the morphological sexing after Acsádi et al. (1970).

Sex coefficient (x)	Sexual trait expression
N/A	Not available – not determinable
-2	Hyperfeminine
-1	Feminine
0	Indistinguishable / indifferent
+1	Masculine
+2	Hypermasculine

N/A = data not available.

Tab. S2.7: Classification of the biological sex after Acsádi et al. (1970).

Degree of sexualization (M)	Overall sexual trait expression	Biological sex
-2 to -1.5	Hyperfeminine	Female (F)
-1.5 to -0.4	Feminine	
-0.4 to 0.4	Indistinguishable / indifferent	Unidentifiable / indifferent (ind)
0.4 to 1.5	Masculine	Male (M)
1.5 to 2	Hypermasculine	

Supplementary Material, Materials – S2.8

Morphological Sexing – Trait Scoring Results for the Eritrean Skull Series

Tab. S2.8: Summary of the morphological sexing results for the Eritrean skull series (n = 21) using the trait scoring method after Acsádi et al. (1970) using the trait list by Sjøvold (1988) modified after Acsádi et al. (1970) and Ferembach et al. (1980). Note that the morphological sexing results do not represent sexes that are used in the final analysis. Refer to table S2.12 for the final sex determination.

ID	Md.	Cranium												Mandible					M	Sex
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17		
RV 1065	no	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	-1	1	1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.48	M
RV 1283	no	0	-2	-2	-1	-2	0	-1	-1	0	0	-1	-2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-1.04	F
RV 1284	no	1	1	0	-1	1	0	1	-1	1	0	0	1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.32	ind
RV 1285	no	-1	-2	-2	-2	-2	0	-1	-2	-1	2	1	1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-1.16	F
RV 1288	no	2	2	1	2	2	0	1	1	1	2	1	1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1.4	M
RV 1289	no	0	-1	2	2	-1	1	1	1	1	2	1	0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.72	M
RV 1290	no	-2	2	0	-1	-2	-1	0	-1	-1	-1	-2	-1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-0.68	F
RV 1291	no	1	1	0	1	1	-1	0	1	-1	-1	0	-1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.28	ind
RV 1293	no	1	1	2	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1.36	M
RV 1294	no	0	0	-1	N/A	-1	0	-1	-1	-2	-2	-1	0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-0.73	F
RV 1296	yes	1	1	1	1	1	2	-1	1	1	-2	2	2	1	1	-1	1	1	0.85	M
RV 1298	yes	0	0	0	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	0	-2	-0.70	F
RV 1300	no	N/A	2	0	N/A	1	0	1	-1	0	-1	2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.50	M
RV 1301	no	1	1	1	1	2	1	0	1	1	2	1	1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1.04	M
RV 1302	y/n	-2	-1	-2	-1	-2	1	-2	-1	0	-2	-2	-2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-1.28	F
RV 1303	no	0	1	1	2	1	1	-2	2	0	1	1	2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.80	M
RV 1304	yes	-1	2	1	1	-1	0	-1	1	2	1	0	0	-1	-2	1	0	-1	0.15	ind
RV 1305	yes	-2	1	-1	-1	-2	2	0	0	1	-1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	-0.06	ind
RV 1306	yes	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	1	0	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	1.49	M
RV 1307	y/n	-1	0	-1	N/A	-2	-1	-2	-2	-1	-1	1	-1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-1.05	F
RV 1309	y/n	1	1	1	-1	0	0	1	-1	1	-2	1	1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.32	ind

Mandible: Md. = mandible (yes = correct Md. is present; no = Md. is missing; y/n = yes, a mandible is present but does not match with the skull). **Traits** (see also tab. S2.5): 1) Glabella, 2) Processus mastoideus, 3) Planum nuchale relief, 4) Processus zygomaticus, 5) Arcus superciliaris, 6) Tubera frontalia and parietalia, 7) Protoburantia occipitalis externus, 8) Os zygomaticum, 9) Crista supramastoidea, 10) Margo supraorbitalis, 11) Os frontale inclination, 12) Orbitae form, 13) General aspect (of mandible), 14) Trigonum mandibulae, 15) Angulus mandibulae, 16) Margo inferior, 17) Processus Condylaris. **Scoring code** (see tab. S2.6): -2 = hyperfeminine, -1 = feminine, 0 = indistinguishable / indifferent, 1 = masculine, 2 = hypermasculine. N/A = trait not observable / data not available, **M** (bold, in table header) = degree of sexualization. **Sex groups** (for classification see tab. S2.7): F = female, M = male, ind = unidentifiable / indifferent.

Supplementary Material, Materials – S2.9

Morphological sexing – Trait scoring results for the Japanese skull series

Tab. S2.9: Summary of the morphological sexing results for the Japanese skull series (n = 11) using the trait scoring method after Acsádi et al. (1970) using the trait list by Sjøvold (1988) modified after Acsádi et al. (1970) and Ferembach et al. (1980). Note that the morphological sexing results do not represent sexes that are used in the final analysis. Refer to table S2.13 for the final sex determination.

ID	Md.	Cranium												Mandible					M	Sex
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17		
RV 37	y/n	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-1	-2	0	-2	-2	-2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-1.76	F
RV 1067	yes	2	1	2	2	0	1	2	2	1	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	1.58	M
RV 2148	yes	-2	2	1	0	-2	1	-2	-1	0	1	1	-1	0	1	0	1	0	-0.03	ind
S 4033	no	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	0	-2	-1	0	0	-2	0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-1.44	F
S 4034	no	-1	1	0	1	0	1	-1	0	-1	-2	-1	0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-0.08	ind
S 4035	no	1	0	0	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	0	-1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.8	M
S 4036	y/n	-2	-2	0	-1	-1	0	-2	-2	-1	-1	-2	-1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-1.24	F
S 4037	no	-2	-2	-2	-1	-2	0	-2	0	-2	-2	-2	-2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-1.56	F
S 4038	yes	-1	0	-1	0	0	1	-1	-1	0	-1	0	-1	1	1	0	1	0	-0.12	ind
S 4039	yes	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	1	2	2	1.79	M
S 4632	yes	1	2	2	0	1	0	0	1	-1	2	1	1	1	1	0	2	1	0.88	M

Mandible: Md. = mandible (yes = correct Md. is present; no = Md. is missing; y/n = yes, a mandible is present but does not match with the skull). **Traits** (see also tab. S2.5): 1) Glabella, 2) Processus mastoideus, 3) Planum nuchale relief, 4) Processus zygomaticus, 5) Arcus superciliaris, 6) Tubera frontalia and parietalia, 7) Protoburantia occipitalis externus, 8) Os zygomaticum, 9) Crista supramastoidea, 10) Margo supraorbitalis, 11) Os frontale inclination, 12) Orbitae form, 13) General aspect (of mandible), 14) Trigonum mandibulae, 15) Angulus mandibulae, 16) Margo inferior, 17) Processus Condylaris. **Scoring code** (see tab. S2.6): -2 = hyperfeminine, -1 = feminine, 0 = indistinguishable / indifferent, 1 = masculine, 2 = hypermasculine. N/A = trait not observable / data not available, **M** (bold, in table header) = degree of sexualization. **Sex groups** (for classification see tab. S2.7): F = female, M = male, ind = unidentifiable / indifferent.

Supplementary Material, Materials – S2.10

Morphological sexing – Trait scoring results for the German skull series

Tab. S2.10: Summary of the morphological sexing results for the German skull series (n = 49) using the trait scoring method after Acsádi et al. (1970) using the trait list by Sjøvold (1988) modified after Acsádi et al. (1970) and Ferembach et al. (1980). Note that the morphological sexing results do not represent sexes that are used in the final analysis. Refer to table S2.14 for the final sex determination.

ID	Md.	Cranium												Mandible					M	Sex
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17		
RV 376	no	2	2	0	N/A	2	2	1	N/A	2	2	1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1.53	M
RV 389	no	1	2	1	N/A	1	2	0	N/A	1	1	1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1.16	M
RV 613	no	-2	-2	1	-2	-1	-1	-2	-2	0	0	-2	0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-1.16	F
RV 614	no	0	0	N/A	N/A	1	1	N/A	1	N/A	1	0	1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.53	M
RV 615	no	1	-1	0	-1	1	2	1	0	1	1	0	-1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.28	ind
RV 721	no	-2	-1	N/A	N/A	-2	0	N/A	-1	-1	-1	0	-1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-1.12	F
RV 724	no	1	0	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	-2	1	2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.96	M
RV 725	no	0	1	1	0	-1	1	0	1	0	0	2	-2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.32	ind
RV 726	no	-1	-1	-1	-2	-1	0	-2	-2	-1	-1	-1	-1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-1.20	F
RV 778	no	-2	-2	-2	-2	-1	1	-2	N/A	-1	-1	-1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-1.45	F
RV 782	no	-2	-2	N/A	-1	-2	-1	N/A	-1	-1	0	-2	-1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-1.40	F
RV 783	no	N/A	2	2	N/A	1	2	1	N/A	0	1	1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1.375	M
RV 786	?	N/A	1	1	N/A	-1	0	-1	N/A	0	-1	-1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.00	ind
RV 834	no	-1	0	-1	-2	-1	1	2	-1	1	-1	1	-1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-0.36	ind
RV 870	no	1	2	0	2	2	2	2	1	0	2	2	0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1.32	M
RV 872	y/At	N/A	0	N/A	N/A	0	1	1	N/A	-2	1	2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.23	ind
RV 879	no	N/A	2	2	N/A	2	2	2	N/A	1	N/A	1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1.80	M
RV 884	yes	1	0	N/A	0	2	0	N/A	0	N/A	0	2	0	1	1	N/A	1	0	0.60	M
RV 886	no	-2	-2	N/A	-1	-1	0	-1	-1	N/A	-2	-1	-2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-1.30	F
RV 890	yes	-2	N/A	N/A	N/A	-2	-1	-2	-2	N/A	-2	-2	-1	0	2	0	-1	N/A	-1.05	F
RV 899	no	N/A	2	2	N/A	2	2	0	N/A	N/A	2	2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1.72	M
RV 901	no	N/A	2	1	1	1	2	0	1	2	0	2	1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1.23	M
RV 903	no	1	1	2	-1	1	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1.24	M
RV 905	no	N/A	-2	-1	N/A	1	0	-1	N/A	1	1	-1	1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-0.35	ind
RV 923	yes	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	-2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	1.64	M
RV 959	yes	-2	0	-2	1	-2	-1	-2	1	0	-2	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	-0.52	F
RV 1007	no	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1.72	M

RV 1124	yes	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	2	2	-2	2	0	2	2	1	0	2	1.33	M
RV 1613	no	1	1	0	0	1	2	1	0	-2	1	1	-1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.44	M
RV 1615	no	-2	-2	-1	-2	-2	2	-1	-2	-2	-2	-1	-1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-1.40	F
RV 1616	y/n	-2	0	0	1	-1	0	-2	0	-1	-2	-2	-1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-0.64	F
RV 1618	no	-1	0	-2	-1	1	0	-2	-2	1	0	0	0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-0.64	F
RV 1625	y/n	1	2	0	2	0	2	-1	1	2	1	0	2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1.04	M
RV 1630	?	0	N/A	N/A	N/A	1	2	1	N/A	N/A	-1	2	1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.83	M
RV 1633	yes	2	-1	N/A	N/A	2	0	1	N/A	N/A	2	2	0	1	1	N/A	-1	N/A	0.81	M
RV 1636	?	-2	-2	0	-1	-2	2	-2	-2	0	2	0	-2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-0.92	F
RV 1638	no	1	1	2	N/A	-2	2	2	2	1	2	1	0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1.14	M
RV 1639	yes	0	2	2	-2	-1	0	0	0	2	-2	-2	0	1	1	-1	0	1	0.27	ind
RV 1640	yes	-2	1	-1	0	-2	-1	-2	-1	0	-1	-2	-1	-1	0	0	0	1	-0.73	F
RV 1656	yes	-2	-1	N/A	-2	-2	-1	-2	-2	N/A	-1	-1	N/A	-1	0	-2	-2	-1	-1.44	F
RV 1657	y/n	-2	1	N/A	-1	-2	-2	N/A	-1	-2	-2	-1	0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-1.15	F
S 158	no	1	1	1	2	0	0	N/A	1	1	2	1	2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1.04	M
S 159	no	-1	1	-1	-2	-1	0	-2	-2	0	-1	-2	-2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-0.96	F
S 162	yes	2	2	1	2	2	1	0	2	2	2	2	2	0	1	-1	-1	0	1.24	M
S 4541	yes	-2	0	1	0	-2	-1	-2	-2	-1	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	-2	0	-1	-1.15	F
S 4585	no	-2	-1	0	-1	-2	0	-1	0	-1	-2	-2	0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-0.96	F
S 4631	yes	-2	-1	0	-1	-2	-1	-1	-2	-2	-2	-2	0	-1	0	0	-1	-2	-1.15	F
S 5164	yes	1	1	1	0	1	2	0	1	2	1	-1	1	1	1	1	0	0	0.85	M
S 5165	no	1	2	1	2	1	2	0	2	2	2	1	1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1.44	M

Mandible: Md. = mandible (yes = correct Md. is present; no = Md. is missing; y/n = yes, a mandible is present but does not match with the skull). **Traits** (see also tab. S2.5): 1) Glabella, 2) Processus mastoideus, 3) Planum nuchale relief, 4) Processus zygomaticus, 5) Arcus superciliaris, 6) Tubera frontalia and parietalia, 7) Protoburantia occipitalis externus, 8) Os zygomaticum, 9) Crista supramastoidea, 10) Margo supraorbitalis, 11) Os frontale inclination, 12) Orbitae form, 13) General aspect (of mandible), 14) Trigonum mandibulae, 15) Angulus mandibulae, 16) Margo inferior, 17) Processus Condylaris. **Scoring code** (see tab. S2.6): -2 = hyperfeminine, -1 = feminine, 0 = indistinguishable / indifferent, 1 = masculine, 2 = hypermasculine. N/A = trait not observable / data not available, **M** (bold, in table header) = degree of sexualization. **Sex groups** (for classification see tab. S2.7): F = female, M = male, ind = unidentifiable / indifferent.

Supplementary Material, Materials – S2.11

Morphological sexing – Trait scoring results for the Greece skull series

Tab. S2.11: Summary of the morphological sexing results for the Greek skull series (n = 17) using the trait scoring method after Acsádi et al. (1970) using the trait list by Sjøvold (1988) modified after Acsádi et al. (1970) and Ferembach et al. (1980). Note that the morphological sexing results do not represent sexes that are used in the final analysis. Refer to table S2.15 for the final sex determination.

ID	Md.	Cranium												Mandible					M	Sex
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17		
RSK 501	no	N/A	2	1	1	2	2	-2	1	1	-1	1	1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.96	M
RSK 502	yes	-2	-2	-1	0	-1	0	-1	-2	-2	-2	-1	-2	-1	-1	-1	0	-1	-1.18	F
RSK 503	y/n	2	2	2	2	1	2	-2	-1	2	2	1	2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1.32	M
RSK 504	y/n	-2	0	0	-2	-2	1	-1	-2	-1	-2	-1	-2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-1.08	F
RSK 505	no	-2	-1	-2	-2	-2	-1	-2	-2	-1	-2	-2	-2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-1.72	F
RSK 506	?	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	-1	-2	-2	-1	0	-2	-1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-1.08	F
RV 1119	no	-2	0	-2	0	-2	-2	-1	-1	-2	0	-1	-2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-1.24	F
RV 1120	no	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1.68	M
RV 1121	no	N/A	0	0	N/A	-1	-1	-1	N/A	0	0	0	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-0.38	ind
RV 1122	no	2	1	2	0	2	2	2	1	-1	0	2	1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1.20	M
RV 1123	no	-2	-1	-2	-1	-2	0	0	-2	0	-2	-2	-2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-1.28	F
RV 1842	no	2	2	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1.48	M
RV 1844	no	1	1	N/A	-1	0	1	-2	-1	-1	0	1	1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-0.05	ind
RV 1845	no	1	2	2	1	1	2	2	1	0	2	2	1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1.40	M
RV 1846	no	2	1	1	2	2	2	0	2	1	1	2	2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1.48	M
RV 1847	no	1	0	-2	-1	-2	-1	-2	-2	1	-2	-1	-2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-0.92	F
RV 1848	no	-2	-1	-1	-2	-2	0	-1	-2	-2	-2	0	-1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	-1.4	F

Mandible: Md. = mandible (yes = correct Md. is present; no = Md. is missing; y/n = yes, a mandible is present but does not match with the skull). **Traits** (see also tab. S2.5): 1) Glabella, 2) Processus mastoideus, 3) Planum nuchale relief, 4) Processus zygomaticus, 5) Arcus superciliaris, 6) Tubera frontalia and parietalia, 7) Protoburantia occipitalis externus, 8) Os zygomaticum, 9) Crista supramastoidea, 10) Margo supraorbitalis, 11) Os frontale inclination, 12) Orbitae form, 13) General aspect (of mandible), 14) Trigonum mandibulae, 15) Angulus mandibulae, 16) Margo inferior, 17) Processus Condylaris. **Scoring code** (see tab. S2.6): -2 = hyperfeminine, -1 = feminine, 0 = indistinguishable / indifferent, 1 = masculine, 2 = hypermasculine. N/A = trait not observable / data not available, **M** (bold, in table header) = degree of sexualization. **Sex groups** (for classification see tab. S2.7): F = female, M = male, ind = unidentifiable / indifferent.

Supplementary Material, Materials – S2.12 and S2.13
General Sexing Information for the Eritrean Skull Series

Tab. S2.12: Summary of the sexing results of the Eritrean Kohaito skull series.

ID	Czekanowski (ID cards)	Jungklaus (2017)	This study (tab. S2.8)	Final sex
RV 1065	M (seemingly)	M	M	M
RV 1283	F (seemingly)	F	F	F
RV 1284	M (certain)	M	ind*	M
RV 1285	F (seemingly)	F	F	F
RV 1288	M (certain)	M	M	M
RV 1289	M (seemingly)	F (seemingly)*	M	M
RV 1290	M (certain)*	F	F	F
RV 1291	M (certain)	M (seemingly)	ind*	M
RV 1293	M (seemingly)	M	M	M
RV 1294	F (uncertain)	F	F	F
RV 1296	M (certain)	M	M	M
RV 1298	F (seemingly)	F	F	F
RV 1300	M (certain)	M	M	M
RV 1301	M (seemingly)	M	M	M
RV 1302	F (seemingly)	F	F	F
RV 1303	M (certain)	M	M	M
RV 1304	M (seemingly)*	F*	ind*	ind
RV 1305	Uncertain*	F (seemingly)*	ind*	ind
RV 1306	M (seemingly)	M	M	M
RV 1307	F (seemingly)	F	F	F
RV 1309	M (certain)	M	ind*	M

Legend: RV = Rudolf-Virchow-Collection inventory number, * = diverging sex, F = female, M = male, ind = unidentifiable/indifferent. Note: the 'Final sex' column represents the sex information that is used for the subsequent analyses in this study. The column 'This study' summarizes the results of the morphological sex assessment by Leah Böttger and the author using the method by Acsádi et al. (1970) which are also reported in table S2.8.

General Sexing Information for the Japanese Skull Series

Tab. S2.13: Summary of the sexing results of the Japanese skull series.

ID	Unknown author	This study (tab. S2.9)	Final sex
RV 37	♀ (F) written on skull	F	F
RV 1067	N/A	M	M
RV 2148	N/A	ind	ind
S 4033	N/A	F	F
S 4034	N/A	ind	ind
S 4035	N/A	M	M
S 4036	N/A	F	F
S 4037	N/A	F	F
S 4038	N/A	ind	ind
S 4039	N/A	M	M
S 4632	N/A	M	M

Legend: RV = Rudolf-Virchow-Collection inventory number, S = Felix-von-Luschan-Collection inventory number, * = diverging sex, F = female, M = male, ind = unidentifiable/indifferent. Note: the 'Final sex' column represents the sex information that is used for the subsequent analyses in this study. The column 'This study' summarizes the results of the morphological sex assessment by Leah Böttger and the author using the method by Acsádi et al. (1970) which are also reported in table S2.9.

Supplementary Material, Materials – S2.14

General Sexing Information for the German Skull Series

Tab. S2.14: Summary of the sexing results of the German skull series.

ID	Divers Sources	This study (tab. S2.10)	Final sex
RV 376	Female according to Virchow (Virchow, 1892)	M	M
RV 389	N/A	M	M
RV 613	N/A	F	F
RV 614	N/A	M	M
RV 615	N/A	ind	ind
RV 721	N/A	F	F
RV 724	N/A	M	M
RV 725	N/A	ind	ind
RV 726	N/A	F	F
RV 778	Female according to Virchow (Virchow, 1874a)	F	F
RV 782	N/A	F	F
RV 783	N/A	M	M
RV 786	N/A	ind	ind
RV 834	N/A	ind	ind
RV 870	N/A	M	M
RV 872	N/A	ind	ind
RV 879	N/A	M	M
RV 884	N/A	M	M
RV 886	N/A	F	F
RV 890	N/A	F	F
RV 899	Male according to Virchow (Virchow, 1886)	M	M
RV 901	N/A	M	M
RV 903	N/A	M	M
RV 905	N/A	ind	ind
RV 923	N/A	M	M
RV 959	N/A	F	F
RV 1007	N/A	M	M
RV 1124	N/A	M	M
RV 1613	N/A	M	M
RV 1615	N/A	F	F
RV 1616	N/A	F	F
RV 1618	N/A	F	F
RV 1625	M according to Virchow (Virchow, 1877)	M	M
RV 1630	N/A	M	M
RV 1633	N/A	M	M
RV 1636	N/A	F	F
RV 1638	N/A	M	M
RV 1639	N/A	ind	ind
RV 1640	Female name written on skull	F	F
RV 1656	Female according to Virchow (Virchow, 1874b)	F	F
RV 1657	N/A	F	F
S 158	N/A	M	M
S 159	N/A	F	F
S 162	N/A	M	M
S 4541	Female name written on skull	F	F
S 4585	Female name written on skull	F	F
S 4631	Female name written on skull	F	F
S 5164	Male name written on skull	M	M
S 5165	N/A	M	M

Legend: RV = Rudolf-Virchow-Collection inventory number, S = Felix-von-Luschan-Collection inventory number, F = female, M = male, ind = unidentifiable/indifferent. Note: the 'Final sex' column represents the sex information that is used for the subsequent analyses in this study. The column 'This study' summarizes the results of the morphological sex assessment by Leah Böttger and the author using the method by Acsádi et al. (1970) which are also reported in table S2.10.

Supplementary Material, Materials – S2.15 and S2.16

General Sexing Information for the Greek Skull Series

Tab. S2.15: Summary of the sexing results of the Greek skull series.

ID	Karteikarten (ID card; author)	This study (tab. S2.11)	Final sex
RSK 501	N/A	M	M
RSK 502	N/A	F	F
RSK 503	N/A	M	M
RSK 504	N/A	F	F
RSK 505	N/A	F	F
RSK 506	N/A	F	F
RV 1119	Probably female (Czekanowski)	F	F
RV 1120	Male (Czekanowski)	M	M
RV 1121	Probably male (Czekanowski)	ind*	ind
RV 1122	Probably male (Czekanowski)	M	M
RV 1123	Probably female (Futterer)	F	F
RV 1842	Probably male (Futterer)	M	M
RV 1844	Probably female (Futterer)	ind*	ind
RV 1845	Male (Futterer)	M	M
RV 1846	Male (Futterer)	M	M
RV 1847	Probably female (Futterer)	F	F
RV 1848	Unsure (Futterer)	F*	ind

Legend: RSK = Former-Racial-Skull-Collection inventory number, RV = Rudolf-Virchow-Collection inventory number, * = diverging sex, F = female, M = male, ind = unidentifiable/indifferent. Note: the 'Final sex' column represents the sex information that is used for the subsequent analyses in this study. The column 'This study' summarizes the results of the morphological sex assessment by the author using the method by Acsádi et al. (1970) which are also reported in table S2.11.

Sex Distribution of the Berlin Samples

Tab. S2.16: Absolute and relative frequencies of sex identified and unidentified individuals per population from the newly collected samples from the anthropological Berlin collections.

Population	Females	Males	Unidentifiable (ind)	Total (Population)
Eritrea	7 (33.33%)	12 (57.14%)	2 (9.52%)	21 (21.43%)
Japan	4 (36.36%)	4 (36.36%)	3 (27.27%)	11 (11.22%)
Germany	19 (38.78%)	23 (46.94%)	7 (14.29%)	49 (50.00%)
Greece	7 (41.18%)	7 (41.18%)	3 (17.68%)	17 (17.35%)
Total (Sex)	37 (37.76%)	46 (46.94%)	15 (15.31%)	98 (100%)

ind = indifferent. Values in () represent relative frequencies referring to the total count of each population. Bold values in () in the last column and last row with the total counts of each population or sex group refer to the overall total count of the entire dataset (n = 98).

Supplementary Material, Materials – S2.17
Sex Distribution of the Reference Subsamples
from the Literature

Tab. S2.17: Absolute sex distributions of the 2D FM reference sample. The newly collected data from Eritrea, Japan, Germany and Greece are not included (see tab. S2.16).					
Continent	Country	Females (a%)	Males (a%)	Ind (a%)	Total (a%) / (b%)
Africa	Africa general*	N/A	N/A	8 (100%)	8 (0.63%) / (0.08%)
	Egypt	373 (50.61%)	364 (49.39%)	0 (0%)	737 (58.17%) / (7.39%)
	Kenya	N/A	N/A	202 (100%)	202 (15.94%) / (2.02%)
	Nigeria	10 (4.55%)	90 (40.91%)	120 (54.55%)	220 (17.36%) / (2.21%)
	Sudan	28 (28.00%)	72 (72.00%)	0 (0%)	100 (7.89%) / (1.00%)
Africa total	5 studies	411 (32.44%)	526 (41.52%)	330 (26.05%)	1267 (100%) / (12.70%)
America (North)	USA	N/A	N/A	138 (100%)	138 (100%) / (1.38%)
America (North) total	1 study	N/A	N/A	138 (100%)	138 (100%) / (1.38%)
America (South)	Brazil	189 (31.98%)	285 (48.22%)	117 (19.80%)	591 (78.80%) / (5.93%)
	Chile	50 (50.00%)	50 (50.00%)	0 (0%)	100 (13.33%) / (1.00%)
	Peru	N/A	N/A	59 (100%)	59 (7.87%) / (0.59%)
America (South) total	3 studies	239 (31.87%)	335 (44.67%)	176 (23.47%)	750 (100%) / (7.52%)
Asia	Bengal	N/A	N/A	15 (100%)	15 (0.25%) / (0.15%)
	China	30 (50.00%)	30 (50.00%)	0 (0%)	60 (1.10%) / (0.60%)
	East Asia general*	N/A	N/A	7 (100%)	7 (0.12%) / (0.07%)
	India	1069 (26.17%)	1493 (36.55%)	1523 (37.28%)	4085 (68.22%) / (40.96%)
	Iran	50 (50.00%)	50 (50.00%)	0 (0%)	100 (1.67%) / (1.00%)
	Iraq	45 (51.14%)	43 (48.87%)	0 (0%)	88 (1.47%) / (0.88%)
	Malaysia	N/A	N/A	15 (0%)	15 (0.25%) / (0.15%)
	Nepal	43 (44.79%)	53 (55.21%)	0 (0%)	96 (1.60%) / (0.98%)
	Oman	17 (47.22%)	19 (52.78%)	0 (0%)	36 (0.60%) / (0.36%)
Saudi Arabia	100 (50.00%)	100 (50.00%)	0 (0%)	200 (3.34%) / (2.01%)	
Turkey	385 (29.94%)	330 (25.66%)	571 (44.40%)	1286 (21.48%) / (12.89%)	
Asia total	11 studies	1739 (29.04%)	2118 (35.37%)	2131 (35.59%)	5988 (100%) / (60.04%)
Europe	Europe general*	N/A	N/A	17 (100%)	17 (0.93%) / (0.17%)
	Britain	148 (50.51%)	145 (49.49%)	0 (0%)	293 (16.00%) / (2.94%)
	Bulgaria	70 (50.00%)	70 (50.00%)	0 (0%)	140 (7.65%) / (1.40%)
	France	32 (47.06%)	36 (52.94%)	0 (0%)	68 (3.71%) / (0.68%)
	Greece	299 (48.54%)	317 (51.46%)	0 (0%)	616 (33.64%) / (6.18%)
	Italy	N/A	N/A	75 (100%)	75 (4.10%) / (0.75%)
	Poland	171 (54.63%)	142 (45.37%)	0 (0%)	313 (17.10%) / (3.14%)
	Portugal	101 (48.33%)	108 (51.68%)	0 (0%)	209 (11.42%) / (2.10%)
Spain	26 (26.00%)	74 (74.00%)	0 (0%)	100 (5.46%) / (1.00%)	
Europe total	9 studies	847 (46.26%)	892 (48.72%)	92 (5.03%)	1831 (100%) / (18.48%)
Total	29 studies	3236 (32.44%)	3871 (38.81%)	2867 (28.75%)	9974 (100%)

* = broad geographical (continental or transregional) data from Zdilla et al. (2017). N/A = data not available. Values in () represent relative frequencies. (a%) = relative frequencies with reference to the respective continental subdataset only. (b%) = relative frequency of the total populational and continental counts of individuals with reference to the overall reference dataset (n = 9974). [Number] studies = number of the studies with data for the respective populations as listed in table S3.19.

Supplementary Material, Materials – S2.18 and S2.19

Demographic Sex Distribution of the Berlin and Reference Samples

Figure S2.18: Absolute frequencies of the sex-known and sex-unknown individuals of the newly collected data from the Berlin samples. For the relative frequencies see tab. S2.16.

Figure S2.19: Absolute frequencies of the sex-known and sex-unknown individuals of the entire 2D FM reference dataset. Populational sex-subgroups were summed per continent. The newly collected data from Berlin is not included. For the exact counts see tab. S2.16. Graphic sex distributions of each population are shown in fig. S2.20 to S2.23.

Supplementary Material, Materials – S2.20 and S2.21
Demographic Sex Distribution of the Reference Subsamples
from Africa and Asia

Figure S2.20: Absolute frequencies of the sex-known and sex-unknown individuals of only the African 2D FM reference dataset including the newly collected sample from Eritrea (marked with *). Counts of the three different sex-subgroups from different studies were summed per population. For the exact counts see tab. S2.17 and S3.19.

Figure S2.21: Absolute counts of the sex-known and sex-unknown individuals of only the Asian 2D FM reference dataset including the newly collected Japanese sample (marked with *). The counts of the distinct sex-subgroups reported in different studies were summed per population. For the exact counts see tab. S2.17 and S3.19.

Supplementary Material, Materials – S2.22 and S2.23
Demographic Sex Distribution of the Reference Subsamples
from the Americas and Europe

Figure S2.22: Absolute counts of the sexed and sex-unidentified individuals of the North and South American 2D FM reference dataset. Counts of the different sex-subgroups in different studies have been summed separately per population. For the exact counts see tab. S2.17 and S3.19.

Figure S2.23: Total, absolute frequencies of the sex-identified and sex-unidentified individuals of the European 2D FM reference dataset including the two new samples from Germany and Greece (both marked with *). The number of individuals per sex-subgroup reported in different studies have been summed per population separately except for the new Greek sample and the Greek samples from the literature. For the exact counts see tab. S2.17 and S3.19.

Supplementary Material, Materials – S2.24

Graphic Documentation – Eritrea

Fig. S2.24.1 to S2.24.17 (from left to right and top to bottom; continued on next page): Eritrea FM sample overview (n = 21). Red dots represent the semilandmark configuration before landmark sliding. Note that some landmarks superimposed by the condyles and cannot be seen on the images from this perspective. Screenshots taken from R package geomorph in orthographic view. Collection ID in lower left corner. Images not to scale. Perspective not standardised.

Supplementary Material, Materials – S2.25

Graphic Documentation – Japan

Fig. S2.25.1 to S2.25.11 (from left to right and top to bottom): Japan FM sample overview (n = 11). Red dots represent the semilandmark configuration before landmark sliding. Note that some landmarks superimposed by the condyles and cannot be seen on the images from this perspective. Screenshots taken from R package geomorph in orthographic view. Collection ID in lower left corner. Images not to scale. Perspective not standardised.

Supplementary Material, Materials – S2.26

Graphic Documentation – Germany

Fig. S2.26.1 to S2.26.49 (from left to right and top to bottom; continued on next page): Germany FM sample overview (n = 49). Red dots represent the semilandmark configuration before landmark sliding. Note that some landmarks superimposed by the condyles and cannot be seen on the images from this perspective. Screenshots taken from R package geomorph in orthographic view. Collection ID in lower left corner. Images not to scale. Perspective not standardised.

Supplementary Material, Materials – S2.27

Graphic Documentation – Greece

Fig. S2.27.1 to S2.27.17 (from left to right and top to bottom; continued on next page): Greece FM sample overview (n = 17). Red dots represent the semilandmark configuration before landmark sliding. Note that some landmarks superimposed by the condyles and cannot be seen on the images from this perspective. Screenshots taken from R package geomorph in orthographic view. Collection ID in lower left corner. Images not to scale. Perspective not standardised.

Supplementary Material, Materials – S2.28

Eritrea – Linear Osteometric Raw Measurements of FML, FMB and FMI including Measurement Repetition Information for Error Analysis

Tab. S2.28: Eritrea, Africa (n = 21) – Linear osteometric raw measurements of FML, FMB and FMI.

ID	Sex	FML_1	FML_2	FML_M	FML_X̄	FML_Δ1	FML_Δ2	FMB_1	FMB_2	FMB_M	FMB_X̄	FMB_Δ1	FMB_Δ2	FMI	FMIC
RV 1065	M	37.04	36.97	37.64	37.01	0.07	-0.64	24.85	24.75	25.08	24.80	0.10	-0.28	67.02	N
RV 1283	F	31.82	31.88	32.48	31.85	-0.06	-0.63	26.58	26.55	27.06	26.57	0.03	-0.50	83.41	I
RV 1284	M	37.82	37.84	37.94	37.83	-0.02	-0.11	28.82	28.29	28.57	28.56	0.53	-0.02	75.48	N
RV 1285	F	35.21	35.33	36.11	35.27	-0.12	-0.84	28.63	28.73	28.99	28.68	-0.10	-0.31	81.32	N
RV 1288	M	35.64	35.86	36.66	35.75	-0.22	-0.91	30.25	30.19	30.17	30.22	0.06	0.05	84.53	I
RV 1289	M	30.69	30.76	31.16	30.73	-0.07	-0.43	24.63	24.36	24.70	24.50	0.27	-0.21	79.72	N
RV 1290	F	32.47	32.48	32.80	32.48	-0.01	-0.33	28.35	28.35	28.26	28.35	0.00	0.09	87.30	W
RV 1291	M	38.34	38.36	38.53	38.35	-0.02	-0.18	31.49	31.80	31.83	31.65	-0.31	-0.18	82.52	I
RV 1293	M	36.71	36.57	36.78	36.64	0.14	-0.14	30.42	30.59	30.60	30.51	-0.17	-0.09	83.26	I
RV 1294	F	30.95	31.04	31.48	31.00	-0.09	-0.49	25.93	26.05	26.12	25.99	-0.12	-0.13	83.85	I
RV 1296	M	37.43	37.37	37.63	37.40	0.06	-0.23	28.14	28.30	27.87	28.22	-0.16	0.35	75.45	N
RV 1298	F	37.79	37.90	38.73	37.85	-0.11	-0.88	28.54	28.50	28.55	28.52	0.04	-0.03	75.36	N
RV 1300	M	41.79	41.95	42.38	41.87	-0.16	-0.51	35.38	35.40	35.79	35.39	-0.02	-0.40	84.52	I
RV 1301	M	32.10	32.36	33.00	32.23	-0.26	-0.77	27.95	28.01	28.01	27.98	-0.06	-0.03	86.81	W
RV 1302	F	37.59	37.52	37.75	37.56	0.07	-0.19	28.71	28.05	28.17	28.38	0.66	0.21	75.57	N
RV 1303	M	36.28	36.34	36.25	36.31	-0.06	0.06	28.55	28.61	29.00	28.58	-0.06	-0.42	78.71	N
RV 1304	ind	35.11	35.03	35.35	35.07	0.08	-0.28	28.72	28.55	29.14	28.64	0.17	-0.51	81.65	N
RV 1305	ind	34.71	34.68	35.55	34.70	0.03	-0.85	27.30	27.20	27.22	27.25	0.10	0.03	78.54	N
RV 1306	M	34.30	34.28	35.06	34.29	0.02	-0.77	29.40	29.18	29.33	29.29	0.22	-0.04	85.42	I
RV 1307	F	31.55	31.34	31.99	31.45	0.21	-0.54	27.06	27.11	27.30	27.09	-0.05	-0.22	86.13	W
RV 1309	M	37.03	36.68	37.78	36.86	0.35	-0.92	30.13	30.19	30.02	30.16	-0.06	0.14	81.83	N

All measurements are in millimetre (mm). FML = foramen magnum length, FMB = foramen magnum breadth, FMI = foramen magnum index, FMIC = foramen magnum category, _1 = first physical measurement, _2 = second physical measurement, _M = MeshLab (virtual measurement), X̄ = mean out of _1 and _2 (these mean values (in bold) are used in the analyses) Δ1 = difference between _1 and _2, Δ2 = difference between X̄ and _M, F = female, m = male, ind = indeterminable, N = narrow (FMI ≤ 81.9), I = intermediate (82.0 ≤ FMI ≤ 85.9), W = wide (FMI ≥ 86.0).

Supplementary Material, Materials – S2.29

Japan – Linear Osteometric Raw Measurements of FML, FMB and FMI including Measurement Repetition Information for Error Analysis

Tab. S2.29: Japan, Asia (n = 11) – Linear osteometric raw measurements of FML, FMB and FMI.

ID	Sex	FML_1	FML_2	FML_M	FML_X̄	FML_Δ1	FML_Δ2	FMB_1	FMB_2	FMB_M	FMB_X̄	FMB_Δ1	FMB_Δ2	FMI	FMIC
RV 37	F	37.07	37.04	37.63	37.06	0.03	-0.58	30.56	30.56	30.56	30.56	0.00	0.00	82.47	I
RV 1067	M	37.12	37.80	37.08	37.46	-0.68	0.38	30.67	30.88	31.18	30.78	-0.21	-0.41	82.15	I
RV 2148	ind	32.98	33.02	33.26	33.00	-0.04	-0.26	26.92	27.01	27.47	26.97	-0.09	-0.50	81.71	N
S 4033	F	33.20	33.20	33.82	33.20	0.00	-0.62	30.89	30.89	31.32	30.89	0.00	-0.43	93.04	W
S 4034	ind	35.24	35.16	35.87	35.20	0.08	-0.67	29.35	29.79	30.40	29.57	-0.44	-0.83	84.01	I
S 4035	M	35.10	34.94	35.38	35.02	0.16	-0.36	32.22	32.85	33.30	32.54	-0.63	-0.77	92.90	W
S 4036	F	31.55	31.49	31.71	31.52	0.06	-0.19	26.73	26.76	26.95	26.75	-0.03	-0.20	84.85	I
S 4037	F	34.10	33.99	34.82	34.05	0.11	-0.77	29.61	29.82	29.88	29.72	-0.21	-0.16	87.28	W
S 4038	ind	35.63	35.51	36.20	35.57	0.12	-0.63	30.15	29.86	30.43	30.01	0.29	-0.43	84.35	I
S 4039	M	36.85	37.05	37.24	36.95	-0.20	-0.29	31.74	31.65	32.00	31.70	0.09	-0.31	85.78	I
S 4632	M	36.80	36.75	37.07	36.78	0.05	-0.30	32.44	32.55	32.75	32.50	-0.11	-0.26	88.36	W

All measurements are in millimetre (mm). FML = foramen magnum length, FMB = foramen magnum breadth, FMI = foramen magnum index, FMIC = foramen magnum category, _1 = first physical measurement, _2 = second physical measurement, _M = MeshLab (virtual measurement), X̄ = mean out of _1 and _2 (these mean values (in bold) are used in the analyses) Δ1 = difference between _1 and _2, Δ2 = difference between X̄ and _M, F = female, m = male, ind = indeterminable, N = narrow (FMI ≤ 81.9), I = intermediate (82.0 ≤ FMI ≤ 85.9), W = wide (FMI ≥ 86.0).

Supplementary Material, Materials – S2.30

Germany – Linear Osteometric Raw Measurements of FML, FMB and FMI including Measurement Repetition Information for Error Analysis

Tab. S2.30: Germany, Europe (n = 49) – Linear osteometric raw measurements of FML, FMB and FMI.

ID	Sex	FML_1	FML_2	FML_M	FML_ $\bar{X}$	FML_Δ1	FML_Δ2	FMB_1	FMB_2	FMB_M	FMB_ $\bar{X}$	FMB_Δ1	FMB_Δ2	FMI	FMIC
RV 376	M	40,19	40,15	40,58	40,17	0,04	-0,41	31,57	30,97	31,15	31,27	0,60	0,12	77,84	N
RV 389	M	33,28	33,28	33,69	33,28	0,00	-0,41	28,66	28,91	29,03	28,79	-0,25	-0,25	86,49	W
RV 613	F	37,36	37,31	38,07	37,34	0,05	-0,73	31,73	31,64	32,19	31,69	0,09	-0,50	84,87	I
RV 614	M	39,23	39,33	39,75	39,28	-0,10	-0,47	31,24	31,62	31,64	31,43	-0,38	-0,21	80,02	N
RV 615	ind	34,26	34,20	34,50	34,23	0,06	-0,27	27,77	27,60	28,83	27,69	0,17	-1,15	80,88	N
RV 721	F	37,66	37,59	38,59	37,63	0,07	-0,97	32,03	31,88	32,62	31,96	0,15	-0,66	84,93	I
RV 724	M	40,18	40,06	40,34	40,12	0,12	-0,22	34,84	34,73	35,10	34,79	0,11	-0,32	86,70	W
RV 725	ind	37,15	37,38	37,71	37,27	-0,23	-0,45	34,20	34,30	34,70	34,25	-0,10	-0,45	91,91	W
RV 726	F	32,64	32,83	33,24	32,74	-0,19	-0,51	25,50	25,86	26,30	25,68	-0,36	-0,62	78,45	N
RV 778	F	35,45	35,53	36,04	35,49	-0,08	-0,55	32,96	32,98	33,28	32,97	-0,02	-0,31	92,90	W
RV 782	F	36,37	36,33	36,57	36,35	0,04	-0,22	30,17	30,09	30,45	30,13	0,08	-0,32	82,89	I
RV 783	M	35,62	35,51	36,25	35,57	0,11	-0,69	27,30	27,52	27,98	27,41	-0,22	-0,57	77,07	N
RV 786	ind	38,83	38,79	39,43	38,81	0,04	-0,62	34,93	34,63	35,24	34,78	0,30	-0,46	89,62	W
RV 834	ind	32,98	32,90	33,44	32,94	0,08	-0,50	30,49	30,38	30,48	30,44	0,11	-0,05	92,40	W
RV 870	M	39,63	39,60	40,06	39,62	0,03	-0,45	28,89	28,70	28,74	28,80	0,19	0,06	72,69	N
RV 872	ind	34,86	34,84	35,90	34,85	0,02	-1,05	33,55	32,78	32,61	33,17	0,77	0,56	95,16	W
RV 879	M	34,08	34,03	34,79	34,06	0,05	-0,73	28,27	27,67	28,08	27,97	0,60	-0,11	82,13	I
RV 884	M	34,75	34,59	35,05	34,67	0,16	-0,38	31,80	31,61	32,08	31,71	0,19	-0,38	91,45	W
RV 886	F	35,12	34,96	35,75	35,04	0,16	-0,71	29,05	29,13	29,30	29,09	-0,08	-0,21	83,02	I
RV 890	F	39,61	39,58	40,21	39,60	0,03	-0,62	32,53	32,33	31,99	32,43	0,20	0,44	81,90	N
RV 899	M	36,78	36,99	36,86	36,89	-0,21	0,03	32,35	32,36	32,39	32,36	-0,01	-0,03	87,72	W
RV 901	M	36,76	36,50	37,49	36,63	0,26	-0,86	29,07	28,96	28,72	29,02	0,11	0,30	79,21	N
RV 903	M	38,84	38,60	39,20	38,72	0,24	-0,48	31,10	31,24	30,75	31,17	-0,14	0,42	80,50	N
RV 905	ind	35,04	34,84	35,82	34,94	0,20	-0,88	29,90	29,90	29,95	29,90	0,00	-0,05	85,58	I
RV 923	M	34,40	34,48	34,80	34,44	-0,08	-0,36	29,12	28,85	28,73	28,99	0,27	0,25	84,16	I
RV 959	F	35,06	35,03	35,81	35,05	0,03	-0,77	28,95	29,08	29,20	29,02	-0,13	-0,18	82,79	I
RV 1007	M	36,14	35,91	36,83	36,03	0,23	-0,81	32,21	32,03	32,74	32,12	0,18	-0,62	89,16	W
RV 1124	M	37,44	37,39	38,81	37,42	0,05	-1,40	29,13	29,45	30,28	29,29	-0,32	-0,99	78,28	N
RV 1613	M	40,06	40,24	40,50	40,15	-0,18	-0,35	31,88	32,29	33,82	32,09	-0,41	-1,74	79,91	N

RV 1615	F	39.64	39.66	40.21	39.65	-0.02	-0.56	32.12	32.10	32.64	32.11	0.02	-0.53	80.98	N
RV 1616	F	33.46	33.39	34.47	33.43	0.07	-1.05	32.90	32.71	33.52	32.81	0.19	-0.72	98.15	W
RV 1618	F	32.50	32.35	32.92	32.43	0.15	-0.50	28.63	28.12	28.60	28.38	0.51	-0.23	87.51	W
RV 1625	M	34.42	34.25	34.97	34.34	0.17	-0.63	30.96	30.58	30.84	30.77	0.38	-0.07	89.62	W
RV 1630	M	38.14	38.33	39.15	38.24	-0.19	-0.91	29.35	29.34	29.87	29.35	0.01	-0.53	76.75	N
RV 1633	M	36.35	36.54	37.00	36.45	-0.19	-0.56	34.42	34.48	35.27	34.45	-0.06	-0.82	94.53	W
RV 1636	F	38.11	38.05	38.41	38.08	0.06	-0.33	31.88	31.94	32.15	31.91	-0.06	-0.24	83.80	I
RV 1638	M	31.04	30.84	31.28	30.94	0.20	-0.34	26.50	26.33	26.98	26.42	0.17	-0.57	85.37	I
RV 1639	ind	38.00	38.03	38.67	38.02	-0.03	-0.66	33.62	32.69	32.20	33.16	0.93	0.95	87.22	W
RV 1640	F	34.18	33.97	34.70	34.08	0.21	-0.63	31.15	31.12	31.45	31.14	0.03	-0.32	91.37	W
RV 1656	F	36.83	37.80	38.42	37.32	-0.97	-1.11	29.94	29.85	30.30	29.90	0.09	-0.40	80.12	N
RV 1657	F	34.76	34.77	35.01	34.77	-0.01	-0.24	28.10	27.70	28.28	27.90	0.40	-0.38	80.25	N
S 158	M	34.11	34.24	34.80	34.18	-0.13	-0.63	29.81	29.88	29.89	29.85	-0.07	-0.05	87.33	W
S 159	F	39.12	39.38	39.80	39.25	-0.26	-0.55	29.07	29.07	29.03	29.07	0.00	0.04	74.06	N
S 162	M	33.72	33.81	33.90	33.77	-0.09	-0.13	29.16	29.44	29.07	29.30	-0.28	0.23	86.78	W
S 4541	F	34.25	34.63	34.72	34.44	-0.38	-0.28	29.01	28.95	29.00	28.98	0.06	-0.02	84.15	I
S 4585	F	32.03	32.72	33.94	32.38	-0.69	-1.57	28.41	28.50	28.03	28.46	-0.09	0.42	87.89	W
S 4631	F	33.09	33.17	33.51	33.13	-0.08	-0.38	30.97	31.15	31.42	31.06	-0.18	-0.36	93.75	W
S 5164	M	39.33	39.37	40.13	39.35	-0.04	-0.78	32.52	32.44	32.87	32.48	0.08	-0.39	82.54	I
S 5165	M	35.71	35.46	35.94	35.59	0.25	-0.35	29.18	29.11	28.96	29.15	0.07	0.18	81.90	N

All measurements are in millimetre (mm). FML = foramen magnum length, FMB = foramen magnum breadth, FMI = foramen magnum index, FMIC = foramen magnum category, _1 = first physical measurement, _2 = second physical measurement, _M = MeshLab (virtual measurement), $\bar{X}$ = mean out of _1 and _2 (these mean values (in bold) are used in the analyses) $\Delta 1$ = difference between _1 and _2, $\Delta 2$ = difference between $\bar{X}$ and _M, F = female, m = male, ind = indeterminable, N = narrow (FMI $\leq$ 81.9), I = intermediate (82.0 $\leq$ FMI $\leq$ 85.9), W = wide (FMI $\geq$ 86.0).

Supplementary Material, Materials – S2.31

Greece – Linear Osteometric Raw Measurements of FML, FMB and FMI including Measurement Repetition Information for Error Analysis

Tab. S2.31: Greece, Europe (n = 17) – Linear osteometric raw measurements of FML, FMB and FMI.

ID	Sex	FML_1	FML_2	FML_M	FML_ $\bar{X}$	FML_Δ1	FML_Δ2	FMB_1	FMB_2	FMB_M	FMB_ $\bar{X}$	FMB_Δ1	FMB_Δ2	FMI	FMIC
RSK 501	M	35.75	35.77	35.97	35.76	-0.02	-0.21	30.43	30.42	30.75	30.43	0.01	-0.32	85.08	I
RSK 502	F	36.79	36.34	37.20	36.57	0.45	-0.64	29.83	29.04	29.98	29.44	0.79	-0.55	80.50	N
RSK 503	M	35.04	34.93	35.39	34.99	0.11	-0.41	29.21	29.51	29.78	29.36	-0.30	-0.42	83.92	I
RSK 504	F	30.37	30.15	30.76	30.26	0.22	-0.50	26.20	25.87	25.96	26.04	0.33	0.07	86.04	W
RSK 505	F	35.69	35.60	36.39	35.65	0.09	-0.75	29.01	29.22	29.17	29.12	-0.21	-0.05	81.68	N
RSK 506	F	37.02	37.05	37.38	37.04	-0.03	-0.35	33.66	33.49	33.79	33.58	0.17	-0.21	90.66	W
RV 1119	F	34.78	34.81	35.27	34.80	-0.03	-0.48	29.82	29.87	30.33	29.85	-0.05	-0.48	85.77	I
RV 1120	M	36.26	36.29	36.93	36.28	-0.03	-0.66	30.95	31.06	31.43	31.01	-0.11	-0.43	85.47	I
RV 1121	ind	41.93	42.12	42.78	42.03	-0.19	-0.76	32.91	32.94	32.88	32.93	-0.03	0.04	78.35	N
RV 1122	M	34.38	34.28	34.70	34.33	0.10	-0.37	27.41	27.52	27.54	27.47	-0.11	-0.07	80.00	N
RV 1123	F	38.15	38.06	38.34	38.11	0.09	-0.23	29.16	29.44	30.28	29.30	-0.28	-0.98	76.89	N
RV 1842	M	39.75	39.76	40.87	39.76	-0.01	-1.12	34.51	34.47	34.81	34.49	0.04	-0.32	86.76	W
RV 1844	ind	35.76	35.97	36.00	35.87	-0.21	-0.14	28.39	28.43	28.74	28.41	-0.04	-0.33	79.21	N
RV 1845	M	30.86	30.35	31.10	30.61	0.51	-0.50	26.66	27.12	27.72	26.89	-0.46	-0.83	87.86	W
RV 1846	M	31.46	31.65	32.05	31.56	-0.19	-0.49	29.17	29.04	29.40	29.11	0.13	-0.29	92.24	W
RV 1847	F	32.75	32.97	33.31	32.86	-0.22	-0.45	28.89	28.85	30.20	28.87	0.04	-1.33	87.86	W
RV 1848	ind	35.28	35.22	35.36	35.25	0.06	-0.11	33.11	33.07	33.32	33.09	0.04	-0.23	93.87	W

All measurements are in millimetre (mm). FML = foramen magnum length, FMB = foramen magnum breadth, FMI = foramen magnum index, FMIC = foramen magnum category, _1 = first physical measurement, _2 = second physical measurement, _M = MeshLab (virtual measurement), $\bar{X}$ = mean out of _1 and _2 (these mean values (in bold) are used in the analyses) Δ1 = difference between _1 and _2, Δ2 = difference between $\bar{X}$ and _M, F = female, m = male, ind = indeterminable, N = narrow (FMI ≤ 81.9), I = intermediate (82.0 ≤ FMI ≤ 85.9), W = wide (FMI ≥ 86.0).

Supplementary Material, Materials/Methods – S2.32
3D Fixed Landmark-Sliding Semilandmark Configuration

Fig. S2.32a to S2.32f: FM fixed landmark/sliding semilandmark configuration shown on RV 721 (included in this study). a) View towards anterior. b) View towards posterior. c) View towards lateral left. d) View towards lateral right. e) View towards anterolateral right. f) View towards anterolateral left. Red points = semilandmarks, green dots = Basion, yellow dots = Opisthion, violet dot = most lateral left point (LL), blue dot = most lateral right point (LR). 3D model shown in geomorph in orthographic perspective. Figures are not to scale. Landmarks are not slid in these figures.

Supplementary Material, Materials – S2.33

Raw Centroid Size and lnCS Values of the Entire and Sex-known Datasets

Tab. S2.33: Calculated centroid size values (CS) and their natural logarithms (lnCS) of all individuals from Berlin obtained from the 3D GM Procrustes superimposition. N/A = CS value not available (for sex-unknown individuals in the sex-known dataset).

ID	Population	Entire Dataset (N = 98)		Sex-known Dataset (n = 83)	
		CS	lnCS	CS	lnCS
RV 1065	Eritrea	97.6670	1.9897	97.6670	1.9897
RV 1283	Eritrea	91.9115	1.9634	91.9115	1.9634
RV 1284	Eritrea	101.0688	2.0046	101.0688	2.0046
RV 1285	Eritrea	100.8384	2.0036	100.8384	2.0036
RV 1288	Eritrea	103.0331	2.0130	103.0331	2.0130
RV 1289	Eritrea	85.9514	1.9343	85.9514	1.9343
RV 1290	Eritrea	91.4302	1.9611	91.4302	1.9611
RV 1291	Eritrea	107.0364	2.0295	107.0364	2.0295
RV 1293	Eritrea	104.3959	2.0187	104.3959	2.0187
RV 1294	Eritrea	87.7699	1.9433	87.7699	1.9433
RV 1296	Eritrea	98.8044	1.9948	98.8044	1.9948
RV 1298	Eritrea	100.6214	2.0027	100.6214	2.0027
RV 1300	Eritrea	120.1876	2.0799	120.1876	2.0799
RV 1301	Eritrea	94.7819	1.9767	94.7819	1.9767
RV 1302	Eritrea	103.3367	2.0143	103.3367	2.0143
RV 1303	Eritrea	103.2503	2.0139	103.2503	2.0139
RV 1304	Eritrea	99.2902	1.9969	N/A	N/A
RV 1305	Eritrea	98.0033	1.9912	N/A	N/A
RV 1306	Eritrea	100.7661	2.0033	100.7661	2.0033
RV 1307	Eritrea	89.2476	1.9506	89.2476	1.9506
RV 1309	Eritrea	103.8670	2.0165	103.8670	2.0165
RV 37	Japan	103.1544	2.0135	101.3118	2.0057
RV 1067	Japan	101.3118	2.0057	103.1544	2.0135
RV 2148	Japan	93.2718	1.9698	N/A	N/A
S 4033	Japan	98.9805	1.9955	98.9805	1.9955
S 4034	Japan	100.5048	2.0022	N/A	N/A
S 4035	Japan	103.2670	2.0140	103.2670	2.0140
S 4036	Japan	89.2215	1.9505	89.2215	1.9505
S 4037	Japan	96.8701	1.9862	96.8701	1.9862
S 4038	Japan	100.3387	2.0015	N/A	N/A
S 4039	Japan	105.8081	2.0245	105.8081	2.0245
S 4632	Japan	105.3066	2.0225	105.3066	2.0225
RV 376	Germany	106.4875	2.0273	110.9511	2.0451
RV 389	Germany	101.9102	2.0082	95.8123	1.9814
RV 613	Germany	112.9240	2.0528	105.3059	2.0225
RV 614	Germany	109.3596	2.0389	108.7923	2.0366
RV 615	Germany	100.0385	2.0002	N/A	N/A
RV 721	Germany	91.6228	1.9620	108.4811	2.0354
RV 724	Germany	99.3330	1.9971	111.7520	2.0483
RV 725	Germany	105.3123	2.0225	N/A	N/A
RV 726	Germany	107.3653	2.0309	91.4746	1.9613
RV 778	Germany	109.0607	2.0377	104.3954	2.0187
RV 782	Germany	90.4006	1.9562	103.7642	2.0160
RV 783	Germany	109.3620	2.0389	99.7462	1.9989
RV 786	Germany	100.4095	2.0018	N/A	N/A
RV 834	Germany	104.5689	2.0194	N/A	N/A
RV 870	Germany	96.2511	1.9834	110.0420	2.0416

RV 872	Germany	110.9511	2.0451	N/A	N/A
RV 879	Germany	95.8123	1.9814	110.0420	2.0416
RV 884	Germany	105.3059	2.0225	96.2715	1.9835
RV 886	Germany	108.7923	2.0366	102.6385	2.0113
RV 890	Germany	96.0785	1.9826	97.6655	1.9897
RV 899	Germany	108.4811	2.0354	112.8764	2.0526
RV 901	Germany	111.7520	2.0483	105.2148	2.0221
RV 903	Germany	110.3114	2.0426	102.8764	2.0123
RV 905	Germany	91.4746	1.9613	N/A	N/A
RV 923	Germany	104.3954	2.0187	97.2011	1.9877
RV 959	Germany	103.7642	2.0160	99.8232	1.9992
RV 1007	Germany	99.7462	1.9989	106.4875	2.0273
RV 1124	Germany	113.5900	2.0553	101.9102	2.0082
RV 1613	Germany	98.1668	1.9920	112.9240	2.0528
RV 1615	Germany	110.0420	2.0416	109.3596	2.0389
RV 1616	Germany	101.8666	2.0080	100.0385	2.0002
RV 1618	Germany	96.2715	1.9835	91.6228	1.9620
RV 1625	Germany	102.6385	2.0113	99.3330	1.9971
RV 1630	Germany	97.6655	1.9897	105.3123	2.0225
RV 1633	Germany	112.8764	2.0526	107.3653	2.0309
RV 1636	Germany	105.2148	2.0221	109.0607	2.0377
RV 1638	Germany	102.8764	2.0123	90.4006	1.9562
RV 1639	Germany	107.1976	2.0302	N/A	N/A
RV 1640	Germany	97.8105	1.9904	100.4095	2.0018
RV 1656	Germany	97.2011	1.9877	104.5689	2.0194
RV 1657	Germany	99.8232	1.9992	96.2511	1.9834
S 158	Germany	99.8158	1.9992	110.9511	2.0451
S 159	Germany	105.4647	2.0231	95.8123	1.9814
S 162	Germany	96.1991	1.9832	105.3059	2.0225
S 4541	Germany	99.9968	2.0000	108.7923	2.0366
S 4585	Germany	91.9938	1.9638	108.4811	2.0354
S 4631	Germany	98.5268	1.9936	111.7520	2.0483
S 5164	Germany	109.0014	2.0374	91.4746	1.9613
S 5165	Germany	101.2028	2.0052	104.3954	2.0187
RSK 501	Greece	100.3475	2.0015	103.7642	2.0160
RSK 502	Greece	104.4739	2.0190	99.7462	1.9989
RSK 503	Greece	97.5386	1.9892	110.0420	2.0416
RSK 504	Greece	86.9336	1.9392	96.2715	1.9835
RSK 505	Greece	98.5761	1.9938	102.6385	2.0113
RSK 506	Greece	106.2703	2.0264	97.6655	1.9897
RV 1119	Greece	99.3866	1.9973	112.8764	2.0526
RV 1120	Greece	102.8199	2.0121	105.2148	2.0221
RV 1121	Greece	118.5586	2.0739	N/A	N/A
RV 1122	Greece	93.6569	1.9715	93.6569	1.9715
RV 1123	Greece	105.2278	2.0221	105.2278	2.0221
RV 1842	Greece	111.7515	2.0483	111.7515	2.0483
RV 1844	Greece	98.5765	1.9938	N/A	N/A
RV 1845	Greece	87.2239	1.9406	87.2239	1.9406
RV 1846	Greece	94.1393	1.9738	94.1393	1.9738
RV 1847	Greece	94.8997	1.9773	94.8997	1.9773
RV 1848	Greece	103.5639	2.0152	N/A	N/A